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Sn Electrodeposition on Gas Diffusion Electrodes for the Electrochemical CO₂ Reduction

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Abstract

The electrochemical reduction of CO₂ to diverse useful chemical products is a promising way to transform chemical industry to CO₂-neutral production. The gas diffusion electrodes (GDE), which enhance the gas/liquid and the liquid/solid interface tremendously, are very suitable for the CO₂ electroreduction. Even if no real contact of all three phases – gas, liquid, solid – occurs it is often referred to as triple-phase-boundary (TPB). This term will also be used throughout this paper because even if not entirely correct it is well-established in literature. The high diffusivity of gaseous CO₂ and shorter diffusion lengths of solved CO₂ in such electrodes enable the utilization of high process current densities. Tin based catalysts are of interest for CO₂ electroreduction due to the low cost, non-toxic properties and ability to produce formic acid/formate at high selectivity.

In this presentation we will show the electrochemical deposition of Sn onto commercial and in-house fabricated carbon based GDEs from different electrolytes. Focused ion beam (FIB) etching was utilized to build a 3D model of the porous GDE. Scanning electron micrographs (SEM) of the electrodeposits showed that different layer morphologies are attainable by changing the deposition mode. A new method was developed for cleaning the GDE after electrochemical deposition. The distribution of Sn throughout the thickness of the GDE was investigated with computer tomography (CT). The initial electrochemical characterization tests of the Sn-loaded GDE, under laboratory operating conditions demonstrated promising results.

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Introduction

The main goal of the European Green Deal is for the European Union to become the world's first "climate-neutral bloc" by the year 2050. The global chemical manufacturing could accommodate only a few percent of the worldwide emitted CO₂. However, the chemical industry possess many technologies, which could support the goal of zero greenhouse gas emissions for this sector. The electrochemical CO₂ reduction reaction (CO₂RR) is one potential technology, which can converse under ambient conditions at least a part from the CO₂ into diverse spectrum of chemicals. Two of them – CO and formic acid are comparably easy to produce, because in the reduction process only two electrons are involved. These products could be further used as chemical feedstock in the chemical manufacturing industry [1].

The selectivity of the CO₂ reduction reaction is dependent on the catalyst used. Sn-based catalysts are suitable candidates for the electro-reduction of CO₂ to formate due to their non-toxic properties, low cost and ability to produce (s.o.) [2-8]. For preparing the cathode Sn/SnO₂ nanoparticles are usually mixed with carbon black [9,10], brushed or sprayed onto carbon paper [11-14].

Electrodeposition is well known for being an economical and uncomplicated method for creating metal films. The morphology and thickness of the films can be varied through the applied current density or deposition potential. Beside galvanostatic deposition (DC), pulse current deposition (PP) is one of the techniques commonly used in electroplating. It is known that morphology, microstructure, hardness, ductility, porosity and surface roughness of electrodeposits are impacted by the process parameters [15]. PP also yields a finer homogeneous surface appearance because it is possible to achieve higher instantaneous current densities during electrodeposition.

The efficiency of the CO₂RR is very low due to the low solubility of CO₂ in water and therefore related diffusion limitations. Increasing current density beyond 5 mA/cm² on planar electrodes leads to increasing the hydrogen evolution reaction (HER) which is competitive in aqueous solutions. The current density could be appropriately increased with the use of Gas diffusion electrodes (GDE) as shown in numerous literature studies. Due to their porous structure such electrodes can manage gas, liquid, electron and heat transport at electrochemical surfaces [9]. In such case, the increase of the current density is due to the use of gaseous CO₂ as reactant (which can increase the diffusion rate), shorter diffusion lengths and an appropriate wettability, which facilitates the development of an extensive triple-phase boundary.

Electrodeposited Sn-films on different GDE are already successfully tested for the CO₂RR [16-21]. However, in the reported studies, the metal layers mostly covered only the outer surface area of the substrate as thin catalytic film. To achieve both a high catalyst surface area in contact with electrolyte and good accessibility of CO₂, it should be beneficial if the catalyst is homogeneously distributed throughout the extended volume of the GDE in which gas- and electrolyte-wetted pores are in close contact.

1. Scientific Approach

In this study the electrodeposition of Sn film on commercial and in-house fabricated carbon based GDEs [9,10] from commercial electrolytes using different deposition techniques was investigated. The morphology of the samples was investigated with Scanning electron micrographs (SEM). The distribution of Sn throughout the thickness of the GDE was evidenced by computer tomography (CT). The initial electrochemical characterization tests of the Sn-loaded GDE, under laboratory operating conditions demonstrated promising results.

2. Experiments/Calculations/Simulations

Chemicals. As substrates 29 BC (SGL CARBON GmbH) and in-house fabricated carbon based GDEs were used. To prepare the GDEs, carbon support (Acetylene Black, AB, Alfa Aesar, 100 % compressed, >99.9 %) was mixed with PTFE (Dyneon, TF 92070Z, $\bar{d}_p = 450 \mu\text{m}$) in a ratio of 65 to 35 followed by dry-pressing at up to 7 t for 4 min [9, 10]. The samples were coated from commercial Sn electrolytes Solderon ST 200 (Room and Haas Electronic Materials L.L.C) and Slototin MT 1110 (Schloetter) at room temperature and different deposition times. As anode a Sn plate was used.

Apparatus.

Electrodeposition:

The electrochemical deposition experiments were conducted with a model SP-150 potentiostat/galvanostat (BioLogic) and controlled by EC-Lab Software (BioLogic). For galvanostatic and PP deposition were used current densities from 1 to 5 A.dm²; the square-wave current pulses used in the PP experiments had an on-/off-time of $t_{on}/t_{off} = 1 \text{ s}/1 \text{ s}$. The potentiostatic deposition was carried out at -1 V vs. Saturated Calomel Electrode (SCE).

The surface morphology and chemical composition of the electrodeposits were determined using high resolution scanning electron microscope (SEM, Gemini SEM 300, Zeiss) with energy dispersive spectroscopy (EDS) operated at 15 kV.

A Zeiss Auriga 60 XBeam work-station (Zeiss Microscopy GmbH, Oberkochen, Germany) was used for FIB serial-sectioning and SEM image acquisition. An advanced air-conditioning system minimized the variations in temperature ($23 \text{ C} \pm 0.5^\circ\text{C}$ during data acquisition). In order to minimize specimen drift, the stub was mounted on a high mass sample holder with a fixed tilt angle of 54° , which is why no stage tilting was required to position the sample perpendicular to the side mounted ion beam gun. Stage and sample holder were allowed to equilibrate for 3 h before the image acquisition routine was started. FIB milling was performed with a 30 kV, 600 pA gallium ion beam. SEM images were acquired in high current mode at 1.2 kV with an aperture of $60 \mu\text{m}$. The in-column Zeiss EsB (energy selective backscattered) detector (Zeiss Microscopy GmbH) was shielded by an energy filtering grid set to 980 V, thus eliminating a large fraction of inelastically scattered electrons. All images were automatically tilt corrected with respect to the cross-section surface. The gradual change of working distance and the shift of the cross-section in the SEM field of view during milling were also corrected automatically. A stack of 108 slices with a nominal voxel size of $15 \times 15 \times 30 \text{ nm}$ was acquired in 4 h. 3d models were evaluated with VG-Software.

VtomexL 450 was used for computer tomography measurements.

Electrochemical characterization:

The electrochemical characterisation of the electrodes was performed in a custom-made semi-batch cell made from PMMA. The electrodes were separated by a cation exchange membrane (Nafion® 117, DuPont). The experiments were conducted with a Gamry Interface 1010E potentiostat. 2 M KHCO₃ with a pH-Value of 10 was used as electrolyte. Hg/HgO (1 mol/l KOH) conducts as reference electrode. A platinum wire was available as counter electrode. The electrolyte was heated and monitored by an external heat exchanger. On the gas side, a nickel mesh was used as current collector. To protect the GDE from mechanical destruction by the nickel mesh, a GLD (SGL, Sigracet GDL 35AA) was placed between mesh and GDE.

The gaseous products (H₂, CO) were analysed by a thermal mass flow meter and online-GC (Agilent 7879A). To quantify the formate concentration a HPLC (Agilent Technology, 1280 Infinity) was used.

For the electrochemical characterization, the geometrical area of the GDE was limited to 1 cm² by a ABS mask. The characterisation was carried out at 50 °C and a CO₂ flow rate of 5 ml/min.

To characterize the GDE the current was increased in 60 s from 0 mA to -200 mA as preconditioning. This was followed by a galvanostatic hold for 1 h at -200 mA.

3. Results

Fig. 1. Schematic representation of the GDE, covered with catalytic layer.

Electrodeposition:

In this work two types of substrates were used: commercial and in-house fabricated carbon based GDEs. For improved CO₂RR catalyst grains or particles should be located not only on the top of the electrode. They must be positioned also inside the substrate, homogeneously distributed into the pores of the substrate where gaseous CO₂ and liquid electrolyte are in contact, i.e. at the so-called triple-phase boundary (TPB). One possibility to place catalyst nanoparticles specifically at these positions into the three-dimensional substrate structure is provided by the electrochemical deposition (Fig. 1). The morphology of the layers, their orientation and the grain size can be varied through the parameters of this technique. This is of big interest, because in the recent years it was demonstrated in the literature, that the orientation of the catalyst material and its morphology has a large influence on the produced products [16,18,22,23].

During the CO₂ electrolysis the location and extent of the TPB and, accordingly, the wetting of the electrode is the decisive factor for its local selectivity. When the wetting zone during the deposition is the same as the wetting zone during the electrolysis, there will be

efficient catalyst utilization directly in the three-phase area. Hence, optimizing the porosity, structure, hydrophobicity and the three-dimensional design of the substrate is crucial and has to be aligned with the catalyst deposition.

Fig. 2. Sn-electrodeposition on commercial substrate with different deposition techniques. a) DC, = - 1 A.dm⁻²; b) DC = - 1 A.dm⁻²; c) PP = - 1 A.dm⁻² t_{on}/t_{off} = 1:1 ms; d) Potentiostatic deposition (PD) E = - 1 V.

Figure 2 presents SEM investigations of commercial substrate after Sn-electrodeposition. Using different deposition techniques it was possible to produce layers with different morphology. After applying DC with lower current density the surface is covered with a very thin Sn-layer (insert in Fig. 2 a). Detailed investigations showed that this tin film consists of separate Sn agglomerates (Fig. 2 a) which are distributed only on the substrate interface. The images 2a and 2c are separated in two parts. The deposited metal is better imaged with the back-scattered electrons (left part of the image) whereas the substrate structure is clearly imaged with InLens detector (right part of the image). A homogeneous film is deposited with increased current density (insert in Fig. 2 b). The whole sample surface is covered with large well-structured crystallites (Fig. 2 b). After PP deposition the sample is covered with a thin Sn-layer, which consists of separated agglomerates (Fig. 2. c). Only few Sn-particles could be observed inside the substrate (red circle in Fig. 2. c). The potentiostatically deposited sample is covered with a homogeneous thick film. Three-dimensional sharp-edged dendrites are regularly distributed on the surface (insert in Fig. 2 d). In-between big well oriented crystallites are grown (Fig. 2 d).

For increased process efficiency the catalyst particles should be evenly distributed inside the substrate (see Fig. 1). The samples shown in Fig. 2 did not meet these requirements. Both investigated substrates were thick and PTFE is part of the structure. Its hydrophobic properties are useful for the CO₂RR, but complicate the penetration of electrolyte for Sn-deposition inside the substrate. To enhance this process ultrasonic bath was used for

substrate preparation. Two different electrolytes were tested. In both cases Sn was indeed detected inside the probes (Fig. 3 a and 3 b) as targeted. It was possible to deposit in the inner substrate layers very fine Sn-films (Fig. 3 a) or well-structured Sn-layers with big crystallites (Fig. 3 b).

Fig. 3. Sn-electrodeposition on commercial substrate from different electrolytes. PP = - 1 A.dm⁻² t_{on}/t_{off} = 1:1 ms a) SOLDERON b) SLOTOTIN.

Consequently, to get a better insight into how the catalyst is distributed inside the electrode, computed tomography (CT) scans were performed. CT is an imaging procedure that uses computer-processed combinations of an array of X-ray measurements taken from different angles. Thereby, it is possible to produce three-dimensional internal and external representations of a scanned object. With this non-destructive method various levels in different directions inside the probe can be investigated.

Such a CT scan of the pure commercial substrate is represented in Fig. 4 a. The blue line in the upper part of the image shows which area from the sample is investigated with a cross-section in the lower part of the image. Holes and elongated cracks are evenly distributed on the whole sample and they reach the back of the sample (not shown in the figure).

Fig. 4. CT scans of commercial substrate inside the sample. a) pure substrate and b) after Sn-electrodeposition.

CT-images of the sample, shown in Fig. 3 b are presented in Fig 4 b. The green line in the image in the lower part of Fig 4 b shows which level from the sample is investigated in the upper image in the figure. The whole substrate thickness is 2.3 μ m. At above mentioned current parameters it was possible to deposit Sn at lower levels until 1.7 μ m – more than 2/3 from the whole substrate thickness. Sn is deposited more uniform inside the volume and a thicker layer is detected around the pores. The white agglomerates between them are from thinner Sn-film (upper image in Fig. 4b).

Focused ion beam (FIB) is a technique that resembles a scanning electron microscope (SEM) and uses a finely focused beam of ions (usually gallium) to image the investigated sample. One tool of this technique is the FIB Tomography. The process is destructive because the probe is being sequentially milled away after each image. FIB has nanometer-scale resolution and can determine the distribution of the object's elements. The collected series of images could be reconstructed to a 3D model of the exact region of interest.

Fig. 5. FIB cuts ($15 \times 15 \times 30 \text{ nm}^3$) of in-house fabricated substrate, evaluated with VG-Software. a) graphite b) pores and c) PTFE.

The in-house fabricated substrates are manufactured by a dry pressing method as described in [9]. For that purpose the powder components are mixed in a dry state and pressed with a hydraulic press. FIB characterization of these substrates shows the distribution of carbon black and the hydrophobic binding agent PTFE as well as the porous structure. Particularly, the inhomogeneous distribution of PTFE can be observed. The highly porous nature of the electrode substrate determined by the carbon black agglomerates and the electrode manufacturing is evidenced by Hg-porosimetry measurements which give a value of around 70%. The volume fractions were calculated: graphite = 69.4%; PTFE = 16.9%; pores = 13.7%. In this case the combined 3D-models evaluated with VG-Software do not give additional information about the element distribution into the probe and are not shown here.

During the investigations it was observed that with time the probes lose the silver metallic glossy colour. SEM investigations determined that 2 h after the deposition fast corrosive process takes place (Fig. 6 a). The Sn-crystallites were destroyed towards the axes of crystal lattice. With EDX a lot of sulphur on the surface was measured. After 5 days all the Sn-crystallites shrink and lose their structure (Fig. 6 b). On the surface remain only Sn-cuticle layers. It was supposed, that electrolyte residues are entrapped in the substrate pores and later dissolve the deposited film. For this reason it was developed a new rinsing method: changing 3 times hot and cold rinsing. After that the well-structured Sn-crystallites covered the surface (Fig. 6 c).

Fig. 6. SEM investigations of in-house fabricated substrate. a) 2 h after deposition b) 5 days after deposition and c) after new rinsing procedure.

Electrochemical characterisation: As benchmark the performance of state of the art GDEs developed by Löwe et al. was analysed (A) [24]. For a comparison two electrodes with electrodeposited Sn were chosen. One electrode based on the commercial 29 BC substrate (B) and one based on the in-house fabricated GDE (C). The faradaic efficiency (FE) for the product formate and the by-products H₂ and CO was picked as a mark for the performance of the electrodes.

Fig. 7. Faradaic efficiencies of a state of the art GDE (A) and electrodes based on 29 BC (B) and on an in-house fabricated GDE (C).

The performance of the electrodes with electrodeposited Sn as catalyst is comparable with the performance the state of the art GDEs.

The FE for formate is even better than the state of the art electrodes by using an electrode with electrodeposited Sn as catalyst on an in-house fabricated GDE as substrate (C).

4. Summary

Sn layers were successfully deposited from commercial electrolyte onto GDE (commercial and in-house fabricated)

Using different deposition techniques it was possible to produce layers with different morphologies.

It was possible to deposit in the inner substrate layers Sn-films using ultrasonic bath for substrate preparation.

Computer tomography investigations prove the homogeneous Sn-distribution in the inner substrate layers.

The performance of the electrodes with electrodeposited Sn catalyst is comparable and even better for formate with the performance the state of the art GDEs.

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